

SHORT COMMENTARY

Factors affecting the uptake of the R21 malaria vaccine in Nigeria

Joshua Dangana *MBBS*¹

¹ Federal Staff Clinic, Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital, Kaduna, Nigeria

The world experienced palpable joy when news reverberated about a promising new R21 malaria vaccine. This meant that the end was nigh, for a disease that was responsible for an estimated 597,000 deaths globally (1). Malaria which is endemic in Sub-Saharan Africa has a prevalent burden in Nigeria which accounts for nearly 27% of the total global malaria cases and 31% of malaria global deaths (2). Nigeria therefore has the highest burden of malaria worldwide. The R21 malaria vaccine which was developed by the University of Oxford, manufactured by the Serum Institute of India and recommended by the World Health Organization was met with excitement by Nigerians (3).

Subsequently, Nigeria's National Agency for food and drug administration approved the R21 malaria vaccine on 17th April 2023 (4). The vaccine was planned to be rolled-out in phases in Nigeria (5) with one million doses scheduled to be administered starting December 2024. So far the vaccine has been incorporated into the national pediatric vaccine schedules in Bayelsa and Kebbi states, the two states with the highest malaria burden nationally. So far, in Bayelsa state 7,371 children are said to have received at least one dose of the malaria vaccine out of an expected 7,500 children (6). Despite these strides, the uptake of the malaria vaccine has been sidetracked by many factors. Some of the factors that have hindered the R21 malaria vaccine update include:

1. Lack of awareness amongst primary caregivers (mothers): A major impediment to the uptake of the R21 malaria vaccine is poor awareness amongst the primary caregivers of the target under-5 populations. In a 2023 study among primary caregivers in northern Nigeria, less than half of the responding primary caregivers were aware of the R21 malaria vaccine (7). An even worse finding was reported among primary caregivers in Southwestern Nigerian with only a quarter of the responding primary caregivers expressing some knowledge of the R21 malaria vaccine (8). These studies clearly show a communication gap between the primary health care efforts by the ministry of health and the caregivers of the target population and subsequent impact on the uptake of the R21 malaria vaccine.

2. Educational level of primary caregivers: The educational background of the primary caregivers significantly influences the uptake of the R21 malaria vaccine. A 2025 study in southwestern Nigeria revealed that primary caregivers with tertiary education demonstrated higher vaccine awareness than caregivers with primary education alone (8). In fact, the crude odds ratio of the malaria vaccine awareness was described to be five times higher in primary caregivers with tertiary education than that of caregivers with primary education. The influence of education of primary caregivers on vaccine uptake was buttressed in a study by Ijarotimi *et al* where a strong majority (95%) of caregivers with no formal education to secondary education had partially or unimmunized children (9).

3. Mistrust about the malaria vaccine: The Nigerian public have exhibited skepticism regarding vaccination attempts in recent times. This has been fueled by historical events that marred immunization activities. This was heightened at the heart of the COVID-19 pandemic where Nigerians were reluctant to be vaccinated due to reasons such as fear of adverse drug reactions, antivax conspiracy theories and religious grounds as stated in a report by Stephen et al (10). Vaccine mistrust in Nigeria is not new. It dates back to the scandal in Northern Nigeria by pharmaceutical giant Pfizer in the ill-fated 1996 drug trials (11). There was use of experimental drugs in trials not consented to. This has remained a scar in minds of many Nigerians who would not allow their children receive other vaccines. A national study across the 6 geopolitical zones in Nigeria further confirmed that the fear of malaria vaccine hindered vaccine acceptance amongst primary caregivers as more than two-thirds of the caregivers were worried about the potential vaccine side effects (12).

4. Transportation logistics and cold-chain challenge: One of the barriers to vaccine uptake in Nigeria is due to infrastructural issues like bad roads and long distances to health centers for immunization. A study in 2022 revealed that the long distance to health care centers and increased transportation costs impacted negatively on vaccine uptake (13). Transportation logistics also impacts vaccine delivery due to maintenance of vaccine cold-chain storage. These vaccines risk losing their efficacy if improperly stored, hence defeating the purpose of the immunization exercise (14).

5. Financial Constraints: At the moment, the R21 malaria vaccine costs between \$2-\$4 per dose making it affordable by half compared to the other malaria vaccine which is a welcome development (15). It is worthy of note that the R21 malaria vaccines are being sponsored by the GAVI alliance in conjunction with the federal government of Nigeria (5), thus providing the R21 malaria vaccine at no cost to the target population in rolled out phases. To enhance accessibility and participation by caregivers, obtaining this vaccine at little to no cost will influence the uptake of the R21 malaria vaccine amongst the Nigerian population. The most recent official household survey data from Nigeria's National Bureau of Statistics found that 30.9 percent of Nigerians lived below the international extreme poverty line of \$2.15 per person per day (16). Hence, it is pertinent that long term financial commitment towards procuring the R21 malaria vaccine be put in place by the federal government and good-willed agencies to ensure accessibility and affordability for the Nigerian population.

RECOMMENDATIONS

It is important that relevant stakeholders in Nigeria's health care system look inwards and devise well-tailored strategies that will facilitate an increase in willingness of the R21 malaria vaccine in Nigeria. The following strategies may influence the trend:

- 1. Vaccination education program:** Vaccination awareness campaigns should be instituted using various forms of media detailing how the malaria vaccine works, the dosing schedule, risk and benefits of the vaccine. This should be done through credible individuals of great public standing, religious leaders, and traditional rulers across the nation.

2. **Enhancement of community participation:** This could be done actively involving women groups to partake in the phased roll-out malaria vaccine campaign such that it builds a sense of responsibility.
3. **Policy framework & financial support:** If a national policy on the R21 malaria vaccine is outlined and implemented, it will invariably improve the uptake of the malaria vaccine. The federal government of Nigeria should actively prepare to purchase these vaccines beyond donor support. This can be done by appropriating and implementing budget needed to procure and distribute these vaccines under cold-chain storage.
4. **Health worker capacity building:** Health workers involved in these vaccination programs should be adequately enlightened on the R21 malaria vaccine. They should be able to know the R21 malaria vaccine eligibility criteria, probable side effects. This should be done to enable these healthcare workers to properly educate and allay fears of primary caregivers (mothers) upon presentation.
5. **Overcoming logistics and access barriers:** Due to the perilous terrains and epileptic power supply in Nigeria, care should be taken to ensure that there should be proper cold-chain storage of these vaccines via acquisition of solar powered fridges. Furthermore, recruitment of trained mobile vaccinators that will be able to brave the undulating terrains will prove most useful in order to increase access to the R21 malaria vaccine.
6. **Evaluation of pilot project and upscaling vaccine distribution:** This can be done using lessons learnt so far from the vaccine uptake at Kebbi and Bayelsa states in Nigeria, the gains and limitations observed should be worked on upon rollout to other states to avoid having drawbacks.

CONCLUSION

A whole lot of promise has been provided by the malaria vaccine to malaria-endemic countries. With the invention of the R21 malaria vaccine, one can say humans are about to get one over Plasmodium borne vectors- female anopheles' mosquitoes. This vaccine is a culmination of efforts of scientists of over 30 years in the making. Its production is quite timely to reduce the rising death rates caused by malaria particularly in children under the age of 5 years. The cutting-edge nature of the R21 malaria vaccine marked by its 66% efficacy level according to the World Health Organization is laudable (15). It is hopeful that this will further steer global efforts and multi-national cooperation in the elimination of malaria in the coming years. Could this be wishful thinking? We will find out.

REFERENCES

1. World Health Organization. World malaria report 2024: addressing inequity in the global malaria response [Internet]. Geneva: WHO; 2024 [cited 2025 Nov 19]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/teams/global-malaria-programme/reports/world-malaria-report-2024>

2. World Health Organization Regional Office for Africa. Report on malaria in Nigeria 2022 [Internet]. Brazzaville: WHO Regional Office for Africa; 2022 [cited 2025 Nov 19]. Available from: <https://www.afro.who.int/countries/nigeria/publication/report-malaria-nigeria-2022>.
3. Joi P. Five things you need to know about the new R21 malaria vaccine [Internet]. Gavi, the Vaccine Alliance. 2023 [cited 2025 Nov 19]. Available from: <https://www.gavi.org/vaccineswork/five-things-you-need-know-about-new-r21-malaria-vaccine>
4. National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC). Press briefing by Mojisola Christianah Adeyeye, Director-General, on the regulatory approval of the R21 malaria vaccine [Internet]. Abuja, Nigeria: NAFDAC; 17 Apr 2023 [cited 2025 Nov 19]. Available from: <https://nafdac.gov.ng/press-briefing-by-prof-mojisola-christianah-adeyeye-director-general-national-agency-for-food-and-drug-administration-and-control-nafdac-on-the-regulatory-approval-of-r21-malaria-vaccine-by-nafdac>
5. World Health Organization Regional Office for Africa. Nigeria introduces the R21 vaccine in a pivotal move for malaria control [Internet]. Yenagoa, Nigeria: WHO Regional Office for Africa; 5 Dec 2024 [cited 2025 Nov 19]. Available from: <https://www.afro.who.int/countries/nigeria/news/nigeria-introduces-r21-vaccine-pivotal-move-malaria-control>
6. Bolaji A. Nigeria's first malaria vaccine roll-out is greeted by an expectant population [Internet]. VaccinesWork – Gavi. 2025 Jan 23 [cited 2025 Nov 7]. Available from: <https://www.gavi.org/vaccineswork/nigerias-first-malaria-vaccine-roll-out-is-greeted-by-an-expectant-population>
7. Ajayi MY, Emeto DC. Awareness and acceptability of malaria vaccine among caregivers of under-5 children in Northern Nigeria. *Malar J* [Internet]. 2023;22(1). Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s12936-023-04768-z>
8. Olumide AT, Aigbiremo OM, Yetunde O, Agnes AM, Naomi OA, Victoria AO, et al. Awareness, acceptability and factors influencing malaria vaccine uptake among caregivers of children under 5 in south-western Nigeria. *Child Care Health Dev* [Internet]. 2025;51(1):e70029. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/cch.70029>
9. Ijarotimi IT, Fatiregun AA, Adebisi OA, Ilesanmi OS, Ajumobi O. Urban-rural differences in immunisation status and associated demographic factors among children 12-59 months in a southwestern state, Nigeria. *PLoS One* [Internet]. 2018;13(11):e0206086. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0206086>

10. Stephen AE, Flourish OI, Naomi DE, Perpetual IO, David UO, Endurance OJ, et al. COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy in a rural community of Nigeria. *Int J Trop Dis Health* [Internet]. 2024;45(6):178–89. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.9734/ijtdh/2024/v45i61550>
11. Ahmad K. Drug company sued over research trial in Nigeria. *Lancet* [Internet]. 2001;358(9284):815. Available from: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(01\)06011-1](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(01)06011-1)
12. Adigwe OP, Onavbavba G. Acceptance and affordability of malaria vaccines: issues relating to hesitancy and willingness to pay amongst Nigerian parents of under-five children. *Malar J* [Internet]. 2025;24(1):36. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s12936-025-05268-y>
13. Olaniyan A, Isiguzo C, Agbomeji S, Akinlade-Omeni O, Ifie B, Hawk M. Barriers, facilitators, and recommendations for childhood immunisation in Nigeria: perspectives from caregivers, community leaders, and healthcare workers. *Pan Afr Med J* [Internet]. 2022;43:97. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2022.43.97.35797>
14. Okereke PU, Kemuel K, Abdullahi M, Ede WO, Okereke WO, Nzubechukwu O, et al. Implementation of malaria vaccine in Nigeria: challenges and recommendations. *International Journal of Surgery: Global Health* [Internet]. 2025;8(4). Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/gh9.0000000000000577>
15. World Health Organization. WHO recommends R21/Matrix-M vaccine for malaria prevention in updated advice on immunization [Internet]. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2023 Oct 2 [cited 2025 Nov 15]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news/item/02-10-2023-who-recommends-r21-matrix-m-vaccine-for-malaria-prevention-in-updated-advice-on-immunization>
16. World Bank Group. Nigeria Poverty and Equity Brief: October 2025 [Internet]. Washington, D.C.: World Bank; 2025 [cited 2025 Nov 15]. Available from: <https://documents.worldbank.org/en/publication/documents-reports/documentdetail/099253204222517873>